

A FIRST APPROACH TO THE CONCEPT OF THE DIGITAL GENOME: AI Personhood and the Assignment of Identity (ID-AI)

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Abstract—The DIGITAL GENOME or the assignment of identity or personhood to entities equipped with artificial intelligence (hereinafter ID-AI) is exactly that: an extension of legal status to a new entity other than the human being, an expansion of rights and legal obligations that for many is considered unthinkable. This paper discusses about (1) the existence of conditions for considering an AI-based system as an entity and (2) the real-life effects of the potential assignment of an identity of its own. (2.a) it's possible place or not in the legal-economic-social Framework, and if so, (2.b) in what way and with what legal attributions. This document is an approximation of the study on the possible assignment of identity or personhood to entities equipped with artificial intelligence, what I have baptized with the name of ID-AI, from the perspective of its ethical, legal and social implications (ELSI), as a preliminary step to know if they are subject to rights and obligations. To discover the DIGITAL GENOME, if one exists, of these entities, in order to determine their eligibility for AI-Personhood. A study that goes beyond the limits of contemporary thought to find symbiotic answers and solutions between human life and emerging technologies; in short, beneficial conclusions for society in general.

Index Terms—Artificial Intelligence, Digital Genome, AI Personhood, Identity Assignment, Digital Identity, AI Ethics, AI Law.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN 1972, an American judge named Christopher Stone¹ published in Southern California Law Review 54 (1972) [1]; a pioneering article on the rights of inanimate or unwilling beings entitled "*Should Trees Have Standing: Toward Legal Rights for Natural Objects*." In this article, Christopher Stone remarked that throughout legal history, each successive "*extension of rights to some new entity has been, therefore, a bit unthinkable*". The issue that I raise today what I have baptized as the DIGITAL GENOME or the assignment of identity or personhood to entities equipped with artificial intelligence (hereinafter ID-AI) is exactly that: an extension of rights (legal status) to a new entity other than the human being, an expansion of rights and legal obligations that for many is considered unthinkable.

Considering the expansion and popularization of the new technological reality of systems based on artificial intelligence

(AI), but in view of a more evolved technological state than that of 2026, Some people ask ourselves these questions:

If in the future there are robots² equipped with AI systems with sufficient capacity to make autonomous decisions or actions independent of the programmer:

- 1) .- **Who would be responsible for their actions? The robot or the manufacturer of those robots?**
- 2) .- **Who owns what generates an Artificial Intelligence system?**
- 3) .- **Could we assign a robot an identity similar to a natural person or a legal entity?** Or at least a consideration as an entity? And to distinguish their individuality within a set of similar objects, a common international code similar to that of a car license plate or chassis identification number?

This document is an approximation of the study on the possible assignment of identity or personhood to entities equipped with artificial intelligence, ID-AI, from the perspective of its ethical, legal and social implications (ELSI), as a preliminary step to know if they are subject to rights and obligations. A study that goes beyond the limits of contemporary thought to find symbiotic answers and solutions between human life and emerging technologies; in short, beneficial conclusions for society in general.

In conclusion, **what was unthinkable in the past is now a reality, and one of the main issues is the need to overcome**

²Robotics: A branch of engineering that encompasses the conception, design, manufacture, and operation of robots. This field frequently overlaps with other related fields, such as electronics, computer science, artificial intelligence, mechatronics, nanotechnology, and bioengineering. The concept of Intelligent Agent must also be taken into account: an entity prepared to perceive the environment where it operates, process the perceptions of that environment with the help of sensors, as well as to respond or act in that environment, using actuators (components that react to a stimulus through an action), in an autonomous way that we can describe as rational or following a logic. This reasoning or "rationality" is defined as the characteristic of responding correctly and trying to achieve its maximum performance in an expected result, as a concept somewhat different from that of intelligence that is closer to that of comprehension or understanding. In the scientific field there is some debate about whether it is more correct to call these entities as rational agents, the problem is that all animals and therefore the human being can also be considered rational agents. Intelligent agents can be physical or virtual entities, but when they refer to artificial entities, we refer to AI as an abstract functional system. For this reason, an Intelligent Agent can also be named as an Abstract Intelligent Agent (AIA) with the aim of distinguishing them from their executions in systems such as computer, biological, etc.

¹Christopher Stone (1938 – 2021 USA), was a judge in the USA and obtained his doctorate in law from Yale University, with a magna laude degree from Harvard. Professor of Law at USC Gould School of Law since 1965.

the anthropocentric vision of our society, regarding who is susceptible to being or not being an entity subject to possible rights and obligations. Fortunately, and despite the fact that sometimes we do not learn from our mistakes in history, in the 21st century we have already begun to accept that not only the individual, as a human being, must be the only subject of law, since there are other legally recognized entities on the planet, such as animals or natural parks.

This question of study has already been raised from various perspectives by people more learned than myself. In an article in the book *"The Cambridge Handbook of Artificial Intelligence Global Perspectives on Law and Ethics"* [2], Mark Fenwick³ and Stefan Wrška⁴ state that the personality of AI should not be dismissed too quickly, not least because of the complexity and difficulty of discussing the responsibilities of an AI system's acts. To this end, they argue that it would be more convenient to understand the legal personhood of AI as a status directly attributed by a legal system, rather than as the possession of a set of qualities or capabilities of said technology that equates it to current entities with personality, such as consciousness, emotions, etc., because here we could conflict or contradict some definitions of these same concepts and with pre-existing laws. For Mark Fenwick and Stefan Wrška, there are no ontological preconditions necessary to attribute personality to an entity. It is enough to create a legal fiction without requiring ethical or moral validation, but simply out of socio-economic necessity. Here, for me, the key question arises: When we talk about an "entity" is when we can attribute legal personhood to this entity, to protect it, give it guarantees or regulate it. **Entities are not mere things, but entities are not always natural persons, can an AI system be constituted or be an entity?**

I repeat that this study that I propose should not remain on a philosophical or metaphysical plane, but should be from all angles, because this is where lies the important premises for the correct Cartesian analysis of the DIGITAL GENOME or the assignment of identity to Artificial Intelligence systems (ID-AI): **We cannot make a legal study of laws or write them, without having previously studied the scientific-technical reality of what AI is**, what type of entities AI systems are. It is necessary to know the object of study, the setting, the environment, in short, the reality, and not to construct ethical, legal or even moralistic discourses on entelechies.

II. WORK PLAN

In the face of the change of paradigms, it is necessary to define order in chaos to preserve legal certainty among operators. In short, it involves rethinking how legal systems and societies maintain stability and predictability (legal certainty) when faced with fundamental changes in how things are done (paradigm shifts), which require the active creation of a new order from emerging complexity.

The current legislative instruments, although useful, still seem to be insufficient and are still a rhetoric of trust and

ethics in AI, whose impact for practical purposes is limited and cannot be extended to everyone. What we are clear about from a technical point of view is where we can start from and insist that we should not have an anthropocentric vision of AI systems.

Work from which it has been started the study:

First premise about AI:

The ideal study, in order not to fall into an overly abstract hypothesis, focused on the investigation of an AI different from the way people think, different from nature (analogue life) in order to be able to solve problems from another perspective because at present, we cannot equate AI with human intelligence or identify it as humans.

Second premise about the ID:

The most important thing in the ID-AI, as has been repeated, is the scientific analysis of the AI itself and establishing certain criteria to determine its unique identity, whether it has it as an entity and therefore its legal capacity to assign it that ID-AI. For example, a list of well-known criteria has been analyzed, which without pretending to be an exhaustive list or priority values, could be considered to determine the legal capacity of an AI system. Some of these criteria are so demanding to determine legal capacity that more than one human being would fail "quality control":

- 01.- Autonomy: Ability to make decisions autonomously without human or other intervention. However, this autonomy must be regulated and controlled to ensure that their decisions are ethical and responsible.
- 02.- Reasoning capacity: The ability to process information and use it to make decisions and carry out complex tasks.
- 03.- Cognitive: Have sufficient cognitive or epistemic skills to be able to understand and process the information provided.
- 04.- Self-awareness: The ability to be aware of one's own existence is something complicated today, but what we could demand is the ability to make decisions. You must be able to understand the purpose of your actions and make informed decisions.
- 05.- Responsibility: Ability to take responsibility for their actions and decisions. This implies that he must be competent to recognize the impact of his actions and to correct or alleviate errors.
- 06.- Adaptability: Ability to adapt to new situations and learn from them. You should be prepared to change your behavior based on the circumstances and improve your performance over time.
- 07.- Interaction with humans: Ability to interact with human beings effectively and ethically, respecting their rights and freedoms and knowing that there are limits to acting in accordance with uses and customs.
- 08.- Human control: Although the AI system can make decisions autonomously, it should be possible for humans to have control over their actions and decisions.
- 09.- Compatibility with the law: Compatible with existing laws and regulations, as well as with ethical and moral principles accepted by society.

³Mark Fenwick, Professor at Kyūshū University School of Law, Japan.

⁴Stefan Wrška, Professor at the Faculty of Law of Kyūshū University (Japan), with a Master's degree in Law from the University of Vienna.

- 10.- Limitations and security: Recognize and respect the limitations imposed by law and ethics, the uses and customs of where you are acting, and guarantee the security and privacy of data and information.
- 11.- Transparency: Ability to provide clear and understandable explanations about how a certain decision or outcome was reached.
- 12.- Reliability: Ability to make consistent and reliable decisions in different situations and contexts.

Third premise about the ID:

I am interested in a **more technical-legal and philosophical concept of entity, as a chain of data that identifies us = subject of rights and obligations.**

The current paradigm of ID is insufficient for AI-based systems. If it is not enough, we must create a new one. Digital identity, unlike human identity, does not exist a priori. During the twenty-first century, this concept of digital identity of natural persons has been created, and it is at this time when it has been given significance, therefore the concept and significance of ID-AI must be created and linked unequivocally to these systems based on AI technology as something different from the human being; The level of trust in the systems (network, users, operators, etc.) will depend on this process of assigning meaning.

Most of the consulted documentation (Court decisions, jurisprudence and doctrinal articles) revolved around the assignment of responsibility for machines equipped with AI systems or the conception of whether they had rights and obligations, as well as their place within the current legal system, but all the documentation dealt very briefly with the existence of the personality or identity of the AI system itself. because in all cases there seemed to be an ambiguous notion about AI, oriented to its purposes, uses or utilities, and not a precise identification of how this AI system is constituted, that is, that chain of data or information that configures, institutes and distinguishes it.

My study has been structured in the following phases:

- PHASE 1: Current understanding of AI and the historical evolution of AI.
- PHASE 2: Identify the technological characteristics that distinguish the different AIs.
- PHASE 3: To delve into the technological advances of robotics and intelligent agents.
- PHASE 4: Understanding what identity is from:
 - 1) - Philosophical.
 - 2) - ELSEC.
 - 3) - Technical (Digital Identity).
- PHASE 5: Analyse the compatibility of the concept of ID and AI based on the above conclusions.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW AND BACKGROUND

Although there are previous relevant scientific publications on areas of research related to the topic presented here, these are on an almost philosophical and ethical level. The most notable articles or those that I found useful are:

- Bendert Zevenbergen, Mark A. Finlayson, Mason Kortz, Ugo Pagallo, Jana Schaich Borg and Tja Sa Zapu Sek (2017); "Appropriateness and feasibility of legal personhood for ai systems"; Scientific article discussed at AI Personhood at CITP workshop on May 11 and 12, 2017. [3]
- Kurki, Visa A.J. (2019); "The Legal Personhood of Artificial Intelligences", A Theory of Legal Personhood; ed. Oxford Academic, 19 Sept. 2019. [4]
- Roman Dremluga, Pavel Kuznetsov and Alexey Mamychev (2019); "Criteria for Recognition of AI as a Legal Person"; ed. Canadian Center of Science and Education, Journal of Politics and Law; Vol. 12, No. 3. [5]
- Pin Lean Lau (2019); "The Extension of Legal Personhood in Artificial Intelligence"; ed. Revista De Bioética y Derecho UB, (46), 47–66. [6]
- Diana Mădălina Mocanu (2022); "Gradient Legal Personhood for AI Systems—Painting Continental Legal Shapes Made to Fit Analytical Molds"; ed. Northern Illinois University, Front. Robot. IA 8:788179. [7]
- Mark Fenwick and Stefan Wrška (2022); "AI and Legal Personhood from Part VI – Ethical Framework for AI" The Cambridge Handbook of Artificial Intelligence Global Perspectives on Law and Ethics; ed. Cambridge University Press; Cahapter 20, p 288-303. [2]
- Pablo Ruiz Osuna (2025); "the legal personality of intelligent automatons"; ed. Aranzadi la Ley. [8]

If we look at jurisprudence or use cases of attempts to assign legal personhood to AI-based systems, we will find that they focus on the issue of criminal, civil or contractual liability for the results generated by a machine equipped with systems based on AI technology, or in other cases, on the ownership and property of the results of a generative AI, the conclusion being in all cases or 99% of them, that the ultimate responsible is man. In all the legal processes analyzed, the conclusions are "Like a dog chasing its own tail ": (1) **At present and with the regulatory framework in force, a judge will never be able to transfer responsibility to a machine because it does not have recognized the status of personality or legal capacity** in a current legal system, in short, AI systems are treated as an object, thing or tool; (2) **the main obstacle to the assignment of legal personhood to robots equipped with AI-based systems is the lack of autonomy, independence or will of their own**, because they are inanimate beings, or even because they are not aware of existence. Historically, there have been several cases in which some countries have assigned legal personhood to inanimate or willless beings, as clear examples that our society and the rule of law can adapt to the new technological reality of AI, changing the legal status of these machines, or creating legal fictions that are easier to understand or adapt to new needs and social circumstances. However, each case of assignment of legal personhood to these entities without their own will must be considered as unique and circumscribed to cultural, political and legal factors specific to each State, which will not necessarily be transferable to systems equipped with AI. Here we have the four paradigmatic situations of assignment

of legal personhood to inanimate or unwilling entities:

Corporations (17th to 19th Centuries) From Roman Law, corporations have historically originated from a question of patrimony (or property). They are legal entities (or artificial persons) created by natural persons (or individuals) in their collective representation, capable of concluding contracts, holding property, and being sued in courts of law. Commercial Law or Mercantile Law arose from the fusion of its forms of societal contracts with the concept of the corporation, as a form of supra-individual ownership."

Maritime Liens and Ships (19th to 20th Centuries) A legal fiction that permitted ships/vessels to be sued and their owners to be held liable for their debts and obligations. Principles attributable to natural persons (or individuals) or companies (or corporations) can be applied to them. The Anglo-Saxon legal concept of "maritime liens" translates as maritime privileges or maritime hypothecations, and is based on the idea of granting legal personality to ships."

Monuments/Natural Sites (20th to 21st Centuries) In some countries, natural sites or monuments have received legal personality in order to protect them, being considered subjects of law and granted specific individual rights, as well as distinct legal protections. Ecuador became the first country in the world in 2008 to recognise the Rights of Nature in its Constitution. In India, there are public officials who represent the rights of these recognised natural entities.

Animal Rights (21st Century) Article 9.1 of the Universal Declaration of Animal Rights [9] states that the legal personality of the animal and its rights must be recognised by the law of each State. France, Germany, and Switzerland state that they are living beings endowed with sensitivity.

After reviewing international jurisprudence, I have also analyzed some of the most relevant cases related to legal conflicts with AI relations or related to the concept of ID-AI, as well as their applicability or usefulness in the topic under study. The conclusion is the same: the current legal system is not sufficiently mature to address this issue.

From another legislative point of view, to recap the subject, currently from the EU and in simplified mode, the debate on the pros and cons of ID-AI can focus on the first documents with legal value approved in this regard (although they only propose the subject in a superficial and almost anecdotal way), such as the aforementioned European Parliament Resolution 2015/2103 (INL) [10], dated 16 February 2017, with recommendations to the European Commission on civil law rules on robotics, and Resolution 2020/2014 (INL) [11], of 20 October 2020, with recommendations to the European Commission on the civil liability regime in the field of AI.

IV. OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The study's objective is therefore to identify the qualities of a system genuinely based on AI technology and, once identified, which of these may have the qualities to be considered an "entity."

If we start from the hypothesis that IDs could be assigned to certain AI systems, in parallel we must define the content

of that ID and its functionalities. But perhaps, if we aren't so ambitious, we can devise a new, more basic and simpler ID content than what we know and apply today to humans, living beings, or commercial companies. This new basic conception of ID would allow us to accept the possibility of ID-AI assignment in a more straightforward and agile way. Comparisons are odious and even more so if we humanize AI systems. Thinking about assigning legal personhood the same as that of humans is a wrong starting point, because as we well know, we are not equal, no matter how much reasoning imitates or follows very similar neural patterns.

When I have analyzed and studied what are genuine AI-based technologies, I have seen that under the name or label of "AI", there are many more types of technical solutions than definitions, although the most popular is the one based on the automatic learning of a machine, which is known as machine learning (ML). What is clear is that without understanding what AI is we cannot develop a definition, without a definition we cannot identify or classify categories of AI, and without all this it is impossible to build a logical and consistent regulation on it. Knowing in detail these genuinely AI-based systems, their innards, the AI GENOME or DIGITAL GENOME, is the first step we should take to be able to make an in-depth study of the legal implications of it, because this will allow us **to find those verifiable parameters that ratify that certain systems with advanced AI are subjects of rights and obligations. In short, to discover the genome of AI** that allows the creation of laws that protect and regulate it; and from there, if the result is affirmative, it will be another job to see the scope and/or typology of legal personhood it has and how to assign or control it, because unlike humans, (who acquire legal personhood from the moment of conception), AI systems must have a positive act of the State in which that personality is assigned, as is the case with the registration of a commercial company.

In living beings, the importance of identifying the human genome allows us to understand more precisely the functioning of the body. In medicine, for example, it serves to identify genetic diseases, thus preventing or developing personalized therapies against them. In agriculture and livestock, the genome is used for genetic engineering in crop or livestock improvement, or in evolutionary biology, comparing genomes serves to understand the evolution of species. Is the analogy I make of the genome of living beings with the AI genome acceptable?

Although **the digital genome would not be so much the technical capacity of its tasks but what these AI systems are designed for; the total sequence and structure of bits that make it up just like atoms and DNA, gives us a mapping of functionalities of what they are designed for, a roadmap, a set of unique information that determines how to build another, and not only of its technical capabilities.**

Here I detail how the content of the ID-AI (AI personhood) could be structured, as an extensive example of a lot of useful information for the control and management of AI systems in the market:

Content Of The ID-AI

- 1) **Legal Identity:** - Name: A unique identifier registered in a global or national database (example: "AI-Agent-001"). - Category: Classification according to the type of technology (e.g. following the categorization made above: intelligent agent, autonomous vehicle, expert system, etc.). - Date of creation: Record of when it was put on the market. - Creator: Information of the manufacturer, developer or responsible company. In accordance with the RIA, the data of the supplier or its authorized representative, other than the person responsible for the deployment, importer or distributor. - Entity other than the creator that has substantially modified the system: Natural or legal person that in accordance with the RIA, such as the person responsible for the deployment or the operator.
- 2) **Purpose and Scope of Operation:** - Purpose: Description of its main function. - Scope: Legal and geographical limits of operation or marketing authorisations.
- 3) **Capabilities and Limitations:** - Capabilities: List of skills, such as sensory perception, data analysis, and autonomous decision-making. - Limitations: Prohibited tasks or imposed ethical restrictions or levels of human intervention.
- 4) **Liability and Insurance:** - Guarantee Fund: A mandatory financial backing to cover possible damage caused by the system. - Level of autonomy: Degree of independence in decisions, indicated on an internationally accepted scale. - Insurance company: Company that insures the activities of the system.
- 5) **Operation Records:** - Human controllers: Identification of the people or systems that supervise or intervene. - Updates: Dates and details of improvements or modifications to the system.
- 6) **Regulatory and Ethical Compliance:** - Certifications: Approvals obtained according to local or international regulations. - Ethical framework: Commitment to standards of behaviour or BCR (Binding Corporate Rules).

And from another perspective, the ID-AI could contain:

- **Unique identity:** A global number or record that certifies its origin.
- **Technical data:** Information on algorithms, capabilities and scope of operation.
- **Legal responsibilities:** Scope of autonomous decisions recognized by law and limits.
- **Transparency:** Record of interactions and decisions made.
- **Ethical and social impact:** Evaluation of its influence on human rights and sustainability.

In short, the content or scope of rights and obligations that the ID-AI assignment entails, as well as the functions, would be tailor-made, depending on which AI system we are granting legal personhood.

V. DISCUSSION OR CASE STUDY

A. What AI-based technology can be assigned an ID

It is important to understand which technologies are genuinely AI-based systems in order to distinguish them from

other software or hardware, and on the other hand, to understand the difference between AI technologies vs. AI Applications:

- **AI technologies:** These are the methods, tools, or frameworks that allow AI solutions to be implemented or developed.
- **AI applications:** These are the specific uses of these technologies in specific contexts.

Based on the literal text of Article 3 of the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 (European AI ACT) [12], the AI System is defined as:

"AI system' means a machine-based system that is designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy and that may exhibit adaptiveness after deployment, and that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments"

A first approximation of what are technologies with genuinely AI-based systems based on the above, would be to identify those that use algorithms or sets of rules and mathematical techniques that allow a machine to:

- Have the **capacity for inference** as a process of obtaining output results from input information or data, such as codified knowledge or symbolic representations of the tasks to be solved, through logical and knowledge processes;
- To function with **different levels of autonomy**, that is, with independence from human action and with the capacity to function without human intervention;
- **Simulate aspects of human thinking**, such as learning, decision-making, giving predictions of results or deducing, providing recommendations and generating content;
- **Recognize patterns or models** of action or thinking;
- **Adapt to new situations**, i.e. what is known as self-learning that allows the system to change while it is in use, by allowing learning, reasoning or modelling patterns (generalisations) and the creation of algorithms that transcend basic data processing;
- Operate according to **defined or implicit objectives**, because the objectives of an AI system may be different from the intended purpose of the AI system in a specific context.
- **Influence physical and virtual environments**, with their inferences. In other words, the AI system not only analyses information but acts accordingly on that analysis and the results obtained, and these decisions can affect both the real world (physical environments) and the digital world (virtual environments), for example, in the physical environment: An autonomous car analyses traffic during its operation and decides whether to brake or accelerate. This decision influences the environment because the car circulates and affects other vehicles or pedestrians. In a virtual environment: In social networks, AI systems can be used to recommend publications or advertisements based on analysis of online behaviour and interests of the user of the social network. Their decision affects the

experience in the digital environment, advertising ratios and even the benefits of third parties.

Therefore, AI system is the machine that integrates one or more AI models and algorithms to operate with a certain human autonomy, an AI model is used to make predictions or make decisions and an algorithm is the logic with which that AI model works; although the concept of AI models is often used interchangeably with that of AI algorithms.

I must clarify that although there are systems with a certain capacity to infer results, if this capacity is restricted, they would be excluded from the consideration of AI systems, precisely because of their limited capacity and that their operations do not transcend the basic processing of computational data. Traditional software or programming that is based on rules predefined by individuals to execute operations automatically, although they have the power to improve or optimize results, I must reiterate that they cannot be genuinely considered as AI systems

In case of doubts or complex situations to discern whether it is an AI system or a "traditional" computer programming, where the limit of the defining elements of AI is very subtle, a good practice to identify genuinely AI-based systems is to make an interpretation a sensu contrario, so here I briefly list the cases in which a computer system will not be considered AI-based:

- 01.- Basic data processing⁵.
- 02.- Physics-based systems to improve mathematics or optimize computational performance⁶.
- 03.- Descriptive analysis, hypothesis testing and visual-

⁵"Guidelines on the definition of an artificial intelligence system established by Regulation (EU) 2024/1689" 06/05/2025 (46) [12]: "Basic data processing system refers to a system that follows predefined, explicit instructions or operations. These systems are developed and deployed to execute tasks based on manual inputs or rules, without any 'learning, reasoning or modelling' at any stage of the system lifecycle. They operate based on fixed human-programmed rules, without using AI techniques, such as machine learning or logic-based inference, to generate outputs. These basic data processing systems include, for example, database management systems used to sort or filter data based on specific criteria (e.g. 'find all customers who purchased a specific product in the last month'), standard spreadsheet software applications which do not incorporate AI enabled functionalities, and software that calculates a population average from a survey that is later exploited in a general context."

⁶"Guidelines on the definition of an artificial intelligence system established by Regulation (EU) 2024/1689" 06/05/2025 (42-43-44) [12]: "Systems used to improve mathematical optimisation or to accelerate and approximate traditional, well established optimisation methods, such as linear or logistic regression methods, fall outside the scope of the AI system definition. This is because, while those models have the capacity to infer, they do not transcend 'basic data processing'." "Physics-based systems may use machine learning techniques to improve computational performance, accelerating traditional physics-based simulations or estimating parameters, that are then fed into the established physics models. These systems would fall outside the scope of the AI system definition. In this example, machine learning models approximate complex atmospheric processes, such as cloud microphysics or turbulence, enabling faster and more computationally efficient forecasts."

ization⁷.

- 04.- Systems based on classical heuristics⁸.
- 05.- Simple prediction systems⁹.
- 06.- Static estimation systems¹⁰.

Taking into account this classification of genuine IA characteristics, some AI technologies are more apt than others for the discussion of assigning **identity or legal personhood (ID-AI)**. In order for an AI technology to justify its consideration as a "legal person" in parallel to the current legal-social-ethical concept that States assign to natural persons and other entities¹¹, it would have to meet criteria such as autonomy, decision-making capacity, and direct or indirect responsibility. Here I must specify that the assignment of legal personhood to these AI-based technologies can be approached with different conceptual levels based on the general definition of the legal term personality, depending on the real degrees of autonomy in decision-making, who assumes responsibility for incidents, or other legal obligations such as the possible taxation for the professional activity of the AI system. etc. In this gradual sense or of different levels of legal personhood, we could think of the assignment of direct or indirect, joint or subsidiary obligations/rights/responsibilities, etc., in short, modulating the legal-social-ethical consequences or implications of that ID-AI. In this context, some technologies stand out as the

⁷"Guidelines on the definition of an artificial intelligence system established by Regulation (EU) 2024/1689" 06/05/2025 (47) [12]: "systems that solely intended for descriptive analysis, hypothesis testing, and visualisation, fall outside the definition of an AI system. For instance, in software for sales report visualisation, statistical methods can be used to create a sales dashboard that shows total sales, average sales per region and sales trends over time. With the help of statistical methods, those data can be summarised and visualised in charts and graphs. However, the system does not recommend how to improve sales or which products to promote. Another example is a software system that applies statistical techniques to opinion polls or survey data to determine their validity, reliability, correlation, and statistical significance. Such systems do not 'learn, reason or model', they simply present data in an informative way."

⁸"Guidelines on the definition of an artificial intelligence system established by Regulation (EU) 2024/1689" 06/05/2025 (48) [12]: "Classical heuristics are problem-solving techniques that rely on experience-based methods to find approximate solutions efficiently. Heuristics techniques are commonly used in programming situations where finding an exact solution is impractical due to time or resource constraints. Classical heuristics typically involve rule-based approaches, pattern recognition, or trial-and-error strategies rather than data-driven learning. Unlike modern machine learning systems, which adjust their models based on input-output relationships, classical heuristic systems apply predefined rules or algorithms to derive solutions. For instance, a chess program using a minimax algorithm with heuristic evaluation functions can assess board positions without requiring prior learning from data. While effective in many applications, heuristic methods may lack adaptability and generalization compared to AI systems that learn from experience."

⁹"Guidelines on the definition of an artificial intelligence system established by Regulation (EU) 2024/1689" 06/05/2025 (49) [12]: "All machine-based systems whose performance can be achieved via a basic statistical learning rule, while technically may be classified as relying on machine learning approaches fall outside the scope of the AI system definition, due to its performance."

¹⁰"Guidelines on the definition of an artificial intelligence system established by Regulation (EU) 2024/1689" 06/05/2025 (51) [12]: "Static estimation systems, such as customer support response time system that are based on static estimation to predict the mean resolution time from the past data and trivial predictors such as demand forecasting for a store to predict how many items of a product the store will sell each day are other examples, that help to establish a baseline or a benchmark, e.g. by predicting average or mean."

¹¹On the dissertation of the concept of identity and its historical evolution, I analyze it more deeply within one of the chapters of my doctoral thesis.

ideal ones to start imagining this new legal identity, and I now I identify five:

1. Autonomous Intelligent Agents Justification: Intelligent agents act autonomously, make decisions based on their environment, and perform actions with legal or practical effects such as executing contracts, carrying out transactions, etc. **Theoretical example:** A trading bot in financial markets that trades and makes decisions with complete independence. If it causes losses or profits, the dilemma of assigning liability arises. **ID-AI Assignment Probability Level:** *High*, because it operates as a "subject" in an environment with clear practical consequences.

2. Autonomous Vehicles Rationale: A self-driving car makes critical driving decisions that can save lives or cause accidents and despite human oversight, has the ability to change a driver's decision-making. **Theoretical example:** A Tesla with advanced Autopilot that makes completely autonomous decisions about routes, speed, and emergency responses. **ID-AI Assignment Probability Level:** *Moderate*, especially considering AI systems that operate without direct human supervision.

3. Critical Expert Systems Justification: Expert systems that offer medical diagnoses, that make legal decisions such as mediation or legal arbitration, or those that manage critical processes in industries, have a clear and direct impact on people's lives. **Theoretical example:** An AI system in health that decides on a treatment based on medical data without human supervision or intervention. **ID-AI Assignment Probability Level:** *Medium*, depending on how much these systems are allowed to operate without human supervision. At present, and in accordance with the RIA, these high-risk systems should always be supervised by man and validate the final decision-making.

4. Collaborative Robots (Cobots) Rationale: These systems interact directly with humans in factories or home environments, making decisions in real time and potentially causing physical or economic harm. **Theoretical example:** A cobot that causes damage during an industrial operation on an assembly line. **ID-AI Assignment Probability Level:** *Low to Medium*, but of great importance to assign personality if what is sought is to protect both end users and manufacturers, resembling the concept of Autonomous Intelligent Agents.

5. Creative Content Generators Justification: If an AI system creates "original" or rather newly created works, such as art and plastic works, music, literature, audiovisual work, the debate still arises about the ownership of copyright and the profits generated as I have already mentioned¹², despite the fact that the current legal trend is to consider them as a mere instrument in the hands of a user, who will ultimately be the owner of the result generated. **Theoretical example:** A model such as DALL·E or ChatGPT that produces content with commercial impact, such as a movie poster, the label of a product for sale, or the script of a film or theater. **ID-AI Assignment Probability Level:** *Low*, despite the fact that

some public bodies have authorized the registration of patents or intellectual property generated by machines in their name.

In conclusion of this first abstract analysis of all these technologies based on AI systems, we could say that the most appropriate technologies to propose an allocation of ID-AI at a priority level would be: (1) autonomous intelligent agents and (2) autonomous vehicles or machines, because:

- 1) They can operate in complex environments and generate legal and practical effects, acting accordingly on their analysis of information and the results obtained, whose decisions can affect both the real world (physical environments) and the digital world (virtual environments).
- 2) Its autonomy generates the need to ensure the consequence of its inferences and to discern the scope of responsibilities, because an autonomous agent, in particular, can make final decisions that are not programmed or taken into account by its manufacturers, precisely because of what I mentioned above about the ability to adapt to new situations, that is, what is known as self-learning that allows the system to change while it is in use. by allowing learning, reasoning or modelling patterns (generalisations) and the creation of algorithms that transcend a simple basic data processing.

In this theoretical framework, some people have begun to use the term "*electronic persons*", with a legal status much more limited to that of a legal person. This status of electronic persons would allow them to:

- Performing certain tasks with transcendence and legal effects, such as, for example, signing contracts or contracting services, and paying taxes or contributions in systems similar to that of social security.
- Assume limited liability, civil or criminal, with financial backing, such as the existence of compulsory insurance or a social compensation fund.

Another more delicate issue that has also been addressed from an academic point of view and I have repeated in this text, has been that of the allocation of rights, which due to its complexity is an issue that must be analysed separately once the allocation of ID-AI has been agreed or not.

What is clear from this exposition on how to regulate the scope of an ID-AI is that it should be carried out with commissions of experts to study and supervise the evolution of IDs for AI systems and establish in parallel public or private accreditation bodies, verification, control, auditing, sanctions, etc., which are necessary for the proper functioning of a future ID-AI in a society as complex as ours.

To interpret the results presented above, once a definition of the content of the ID-AI has been developed, it is necessary to understand its potential functionalities, that is, a first analysis of the theoretical and practical implications of the findings, and if appropriate, to suggest or leave open the question for future research and where these should go; in other words, decode/decipher its digital genome.

Once the first structure of the hypothetical Genome of an AI System has been developed, it is evident that generating or identifying the authentic AI genome could be a very useful

¹²Regarding the recent judicial decisions on artistic creations generated with AI systems, I analyze it more deeply within one of the chapters of my doctoral thesis.

step for the legal and practical derivations of the ID-AI assignment, because it would serve, among other things, as:

- Unique identifier: As is currently the chassis number of a machine or the IMEI in mobile telephony to differentiate different AI systems.
- Audit and trace AI interactions: Identify the origin, responsibilities and configurations of the system.
- AI model compatibility: Determine whether an AI model is suitable for a specific task or environment, or to be incorporated into other complex AI systems.

As for the functionalities of this unique identifier ID-AI, the following are easily appreciated:

- 1) **Identity vis-à-vis third parties:** Differentiate and identify it in the same way as a tax number, ID card or passport.
- 2) **Ability to Conclude Contracts:** The system can sign digital contracts with people or other AIs.
- 3) **Limited Legal Liability:** Similar to a limited liability company, it can assume civil or criminal liability with guarantees of indemnity or deprivation of operation.
- 4) **Financial Resilience:** Ability to manage a financial fund to cover liabilities such as fines or compensation.
- 5) **Ability to Access Digital Resources identifying themselves as AI:** Authorisation to use digital infrastructure, such as servers, virtual bank accounts, or networks, depending on their tasks, access to electronic offices of the Public Administration, etc.
- 6) **Revocation of Rights:** In case of malfunction or legal violations, the system may be temporarily suspended or permanently disabled.

By way of summary and as a simple first theoretical exercise of synthesis, in parallel to the scientific analysis of the AI genome or the digital identity of AI, these are some of the options for the scope of legal status of ID-AI:

- 1) **Limited legal personhood:** The AI-powered system would have some legal rights and obligations, but not all the rights that are granted to a natural person. This could include property rights, copyrights, and certain legal responsibilities or you could have a legal obligation, such as tax contribution, to meet certain safety and quality standards, but not full political or civil rights, such as freedom of speech. This entity would not be considered a completely autonomous entity with the ability to make independent decisions, which is sometimes not entirely true in some AI applied to robotics. This approach would seek to resolve the practical aspects of the assignment of legal personhood, such as the ability to contract or be sued in the event of harm caused by the AI system.
- 2) **Collective legal personhood:** The AI-powered system would be seen as a collective entity composed of its programmers, users, and other stakeholders. In this case, for example, an AI robot would have legal rights and obligations that would be attributed to this collective entity, and not to the robot itself.
- 3) **Commercial legal personhood:** The system provided with AI would have all the legal rights and obligations that are granted to a legal entity such as corporations

or commercial partnerships, and that is presented as the easiest option to implement due to the legal background that exists.

- 4) **Full legal personhood:** The AI-powered system would have all the legal rights and obligations that are granted to a natural person that include political and civil rights (fundamental rights). Clearly this option is the most controversial and poses significant scientific, social, legal and ethical challenges.
- 5) **Liability without personality:** Instead of granting legal personhood to the AI-powered system, separate legal liability should be established for them. In other words, AI robots would not have legal personhood in themselves, but could be held liable for their actions and forced to compensate people affected by their behavior, which would lead to insurance or assets. Subsidiarily, we would always have the owner, programmer or executor user in charge of it as responsible.

But if we go back to the genesis of the concept of legal identity¹³, perhaps it would be enough to start the assignment of an ID-AI in a simpler way. By way of summary, it should be remembered that personal identity or legal personhood in general, that is, that which is assigned to natural persons, is legally provided for at the national and constitutional level, by the Treaty of the European Union, and essentially by administrative law, which regulates the functionalities of public registries, such as the Civil Registry where we must register the newborns and whose entry in the registry books gives us the right to obtain a National Identity Document (DNI)¹⁴ and a Passport number, as a unique, personal and non-transferable document that allows us to identify ourselves in a standard and easy way, or rather, to accredit ourselves to a third party without the need to resort to all the registration data. Therefore, **personal identity is defined as the complex results of personal data contained in these public records, which serve to identify us as individuals and distinguish them unequivocally and reliably from others, which in turn can be linked with those of the parents, and other ascendants:**

- - The name,
- - the surname,
- - the date,
- - the place of birth,
- - parents' names,
- - Grandparents' names.

In this physical environment, we could call that identity that is provided to us by a public institution, as a base identity, and the same would happen for the legal person understood as a moral or artificial person assigned to corporations. Therefore, we can have a simpler unique identifier number, which is

¹³I analyze the concept of identity and its historical evolution in more depth in one of the chapters of my doctoral thesis.

¹⁴Ley Orgánica 4/2015, de 30 de marzo, de protección de la seguridad ciudadana (on the Protection of Public Security) recognises the right of all Spaniards to be issued with a National Identity Document (DNI), which is given sufficient value to accredit, on its own, the identity of persons and grants it the protection that public and official documents are recognised by the legal system. [13]

sufficient to identify us to third parties, and other more detailed information about identity, in a register linked to that identifier (for natural persons: birth, nationality, medical history; for legal persons: Constitution, founding statutes, annual accounts, etc.).

As an example, the WIPO (*World Intellectual Property Organization*), in 2023 issued a report on the "*Global Identifier Project*" GID that could serve as an example of this ID-AI as a **global unique identifier**. At the WIPO level, the functionality of GIDs would aim to facilitate a more efficient and seamless online service experience in the intellectual property ecosystem. This GID would serve to uniquely, consistently, accurately, and securely identify a natural person or legal entity for all intellectual property systems and jurisdictions, and could be as simple as for Natural Person to contain name, email, and date of birth; or for Legal Person, its corporate name, email and cooperation registration number or tax ID; they may be issued by any participating authority and accepted by all. But in other environments, for individuals, the GID would consist of a unique personal code generated from biometric data, intended to allow the holder to access different types of services as a unique international identification form, generated from a user's fingerprint that would be translated into a 15-character alphanumeric code.

By translating this concept to AI systems, we could use GIB to assign a unique identity to any AI system that needs accurate and globally valid identification crucial to:

- 1) **Ensures uniqueness:** The possibility of two AI systems receiving the same ID would be avoided, which could lead to confusion or errors in interconnected systems.
- 2) **Interoperability:** It would allow AI systems to be recognized and operational in different environments.
- 3) **Traceability and control:** It would ensure that all actions of an AI system or AI systems were immutably and auditably recorded.

In this ID-AI assignment we must also look for technological and international standards such as an ID Manager and an Identity and Access Manager (IDM and IAM) to guarantee the secure operation in the correct identification of AI systems that have an identity number assigned; or some relevant standards and legislative frameworks such as:

- ISO/IEC 24760 [14]: Regarding identity management frameworks.
- FIDO (Fast Identity Online) [15]: A standard that promotes passwordless authentication using biometrics and hardware keys.
- NIST Digital Identity Guidelines [16]: Guides for authentication and management of digital identities, focused on security and privacy.
- ISO 42001:2023 [17]: Focused on Artificial Intelligence Management Systems (AIMS). This standard establishes guidelines for the development and responsible use of AI, addressing aspects such as transparency, reliability and risk assessment. It also promotes the ethical integration and continuous oversight of AI systems in public and private organizations.
- ISO/IEC JTC 1 SC 42 [18]: A specific committee that

develops international standards on terminology, framework, and lifecycle management for AI-based systems. This committee collaborates with the European private bodies, The European Committee for Standardization (CEN) and The European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC) [19] to ensure alignment with European regulations, prioritizing safety and user rights.

These elements could not only facilitate security and efficiency in identity management in AI systems, but also the pillars for designing a robust and reliable identification system.

And how to manage these ID-AIs? An identity manager (ID) for AI technologies would be a dynamic system specifically designed to handle the digital and operational identities of AI systems, using analogies of IAM/IDM systems but adapted for non-human entities. The advantages would be obvious:

- 1) **Legal Accountability:** Improves legal accountability by assigning traceability to decisions in AI systems. For example, in an AI medical diagnostic system, if a medical error is identified, the activity log helps determine whether the fault was the AI system, the human operator, or another factor.
- 2) **Automatic regulatory compliance:** Facilitates regulatory compliance in AI-regulated jurisdictions, depending on the jurisdiction applicable to your inferences.
- 3) **Security and trust:** Foster public trust in AI systems by offering greater transparency and control.

This system would be transcendental for the peaceful, effective and safe coexistence of humans and AI systems in future society.

Below is a practical and imaginative proposal of what this ID-AI manager made with the help of ChatGPT would be like based on my instructions and the structure of IAM/IDM systems:

- 1) **Unique Identity and Tracking:** Each AI system would have a globally unique identifier (GID) [20], similar to the chassis number of a vehicle engine, ISBN from the books, or an IP address, to ensure its traceability and legitimacy in virtual and physical environments.
 - Composition of the ID-AI:
 - Primary Key (UUID)
 - Model Version
 - Registered Owner/Operator
 - Safety and ethics certificates.
- 2) **Multi-Level Authentication:** The system would use advanced authentication to verify the AI system before interacting or executing processes. Examples:
 - Cryptographic key associated with the GID.
 - Behavioral authentication: unique patterns of decisions made by AI.
 - "Processing fingerprint" recognition: digital signatures of the unique algorithms used by the agent.
- 3) **Dynamic Governance and Authorization:** The manager would define the legal, ethical, and operational limits of AI. Through a policy engine, it would regulate:
 - Access to critical or sensitive resources.

- Execution of autonomous decisions, blocking actions that exceed their level of authorization.
- 4) **Activity Log and Transparency:** Implements an immutable blockchain-based ledger¹⁵ to record all AI system activities. This record would be essential for the traceability of the system, and to be able to subsequently carry out legal audits or ethical and regulatory impact assessments of rights and freedoms:
- Actions executed.
 - Interactions with humans or other systems.
 - Critical decisions and their justifications.
- 5) **Modularity and Scalability**
- Management by domains: each AI system could belong to different domains (industrial, governmental, domestic), with specific restrictions depending on the context.
 - Interoperability: compatible with other international IAM systems.
- 6) **Advanced Features**
- Controlled autonomy: Allowing AI systems to execute certain decisions without human intervention, but with self-imposed limits.
 - Continuous performance evaluation: The manager monitors the AI to detect biases or failures, and generates alerts.
 - Adaptive identity: The manager would update the identity profile according to changes in the agent's capabilities, without modifying the original unique identification code, as would happen with the change of names of natural persons.

These criteria are easily transferable to a physical, tangible entity, such as a machine, but they require further technical development when we consider an AI system, which lacks this "corporeality."

VI. METHODOLOGY

The research primarily uses qualitative methods through extensive literature review, conceptual analysis, and analogical reasoning, as well as a comparative study of current laws and jurisprudence on the matter. It aims to develop a theoretical framework and propose a solution (the "DIGITAL GENOME" and ID-AI concept) to the complex problem of assigning identity to AI systems, moving the debate from speculative to operational.

Here's a breakdown of the research methods used:

- **Legal and Doctrinal Analysis:**

- 1) **Review of Legislative History and Doctrinal Positions:** The study extensively reviews existing legal frameworks and scholarly opinions related to AI, legal personhood, and liability. This includes analyzing European Parliament Resolutions (e.g., 2015/2103 (INL) [10], 2020/2014 (INL) [11]) and the EU's AI Act [12], along with relevant recitals and directives.

¹⁵Ledger: Hardware wallet designed to manage cryptocurrencies such as bitcoin (BTC) and ether (ETH) offline.

- 2) **Interpretation of Legal Concepts:** I delve into fundamental legal concepts such as the meaning of "entity/person" and "identity" in a legal context, questioning their applicability to AI systems.

- **Comparative Studies and Analogies:**

- 1) **Biological Genome Analogy:** A significant part of the methodology involves drawing a detailed analogy between the human biological genome and a proposed "DIGITAL GENOME" for AI systems. This serves as a foundational element for defining the content of an AI's identity.
- 2) **Historical Legal Personhood Examples:** The research examines historical cases where legal personhood was extended to non-human entities (e.g., corporations, ships, natural sites, animals) to explore precedents for assigning identity to AI.
- **Algorithmic Transparency Assessment and Technical Understanding:**
- 1) **Defining AI Systems:** A crucial step is to discern which technologies are genuinely AI-based systems, differentiating them from traditional software or automated systems. This involves a detailed analysis of terms like AI Systems, AI Models, and AI Algorithms based on established definitions from the EU AI Act and OECD [21].
- 2) **Criteria for AI Identity:** The study identifies and analyzes criteria for determining the legal capacity of an AI system, such as autonomy, reasoning capacity, self-awareness, responsibility, adaptability, and transparency.

- **Case Studies of AI Implementation in Legal Contexts:**

- 1) A brief analysis of practical cases like Tesla [22], The DAO [23], COMPAS [24], TAY [25], Uber https://oag.ca.gov/system/files/attachments/press-docs/uber-final-judgmentscanned_0.pdf, exams GCSE Advanced Level [26], ClearView [27], Dabus https://www.uspto.gov/sites/default/files/documents/16524350_22apr2020.pdf, and Stable Diffusion [28]. While not detailed individual case studies, they serve as illustrative examples of the challenges in assigning liability and identity to AI.

This research adopts an interdisciplinary approach, bridging the gap between Computer Science and Law. By analyzing the EU AI Act [29] and contemporary technical standards, we evaluate the readiness of current systems for identity assignment.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

During my PhD study program in AI at the UPC (Department of Computer Science at Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya) these past 6 years, I came to the conclusion that the technical and legal positions that we have to date are insufficient and inefficient answers for the current reality and the technological future of AI, so it is necessary to orient the study differently, almost taking a step backwards.

To return to the initial key question: Are systems genuinely based on AI technology, a real entities?, do they have an ID, a DIGITAL GENOME?; if we resolve this question, then but not before, we will be able to discuss whether they are holders of rights and obligations as David J. Gunkel postulates when he talks about believing that machines should have rights [30] or if they can be held responsible. We are not interested in knowing that at this stage, but rather in whether they are entities with sufficient identity, to discover these characteristics that identify them as a unique and recognizable entity as such, and therefore, the effects on real life for their place in economic play, with the consequent legal attributions.

It is essential to abandon the purely ethical or philosophical approach and start from a technical, precise and up-to-date understanding of what truly constitutes an AI system.

The initial hypothesis – whether systems genuinely based on AI technologies can be considered entities capable of being endowed with legal personhood – is concluded that the answer is affirmative, as long as specific technical criteria are met through a matrix of at least twelve verifiable criteria, such as autonomy, reasoning, adaptability, social interaction, responsibility and traceability, among others. These criteria have been systematized in what has been defined as the **DIGITAL GENOME**, a structuring concept that allows the delimitation and recognition of the intrinsic conditions/characteristics of an AI system to be considered as a legally identifiable entity, that is, the concept of the DIGITAL GENOME as a tool to identify the constituent elements that allow an AI system to be reasoned as an autonomous entity and differentiable from others, and therefore, potentially susceptible to legal personhood.

This statement does not imply humanizing AI, but recognizing its real impact on the legal-social ecosystem through a regulatory logic compatible with current law.

From a practical point of view, the results of this research can be used as a basis for the drafting of future specific regulatory guidelines – such as a Code of Conduct for the Allocation of ID-AI – that will serve both the legislator and the technology industry. In summary, this approach allows the legislator to design a specific legal identity assignment model for advanced AI systems, similar to the identification and regulation regime applicable to legal persons. Ultimately, this opens up the possibility of proactive regulation of all the sectors involved, public and private, offering the AI industry a framework for responsible, transparent design with full traceability consistent with technological evolution and with the ability to anticipate conflicts, rather than simply responding to them a posteriori.

Postponing this debate or keeping it in the realm of speculation will only contribute to a greater gap between the dizzying development of AI, like any technology, and its convenient integration into legal frameworks. This work is a necessary and urgent debate because AI is a reality and as the Latin proverb says "Ubi Societas, ibi ius": what exists and is part of society must be regulated.

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